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Philosophical heritage of Turkestan enlighteners and its importance in the study of social sciences

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Abstract: The article explores the significance of the philosophical ideas and views of Turkestan educators in the teaching of social sciences. The author reveals the scientific and methodological significance of the Jadid heritage. The works of Turkestan enlighteners are considered as an important scientific -philosophical source.

Key words: enlightener, history, philosophy, societies, Jadids, social sciences, heritage, idea, development.

1 Introduction

In the context of the development of new Uzbekistan, an important place in the process of revival and growth of national self-awareness, a sense of national pride for student youth, is occupied by historical memory, deep knowledge of the objective and true history of the native land. spiritual, moral and political culture of student youth. In the conditions of civil society, a spiritually developed specialist is distinguished by conscious service to the Fatherland - the land, on When turning to the history of Uzbekistan, including the content of the philosophical heritage of Turkestan enlighteners, it is necessary to remember that this is the “memory of the people” and therefore requires a careful and respectful attitude. The history of the native land requires a conscious approach, to think about the political and socio-economic motives of what is happening, behind which are the successes and difficulties of building a sovereign, democratic and legal, social, secular state.

2 Materials and methods

Consequently, a look at the continuous chain of formation and development of the new Uzbekistan must remain clear, inquisitive and attentive in order to see the trends of its development. Thus, social sciences shape the worldview, patriotism, improve the intellect and enhance the one with whom he was born and raised. Leaders of Turkestan enlighteners Fayzulla Khojaev, Abdurauf Fitrat, Sadridin Aini, Mirzo Mukhiddin Mansurov, Majid Kadyri, Mahmudkhoja Behbudi, Abdullah Kadiri, Mirzo Mukhiddin Mansurov, Majid Kadyri, Munavar Kori Abdurashidkxonov, Salokhidin Majidi, Abdulhamid Chulpon, Usmonkhoja Pulathodjaev and others contributed invaluable contribution to development of philosophical thought.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted that it is necessary “to develop the national idea, which is a source of inspiration and strength for us in achieving our high goals. We need to strengthen national self-awareness, study more deeply the ancient and rich history of our Motherland, intensify research work in this direction, and fully support the activities of scientists in the humanities. An assessment of the past must be objective, most importantly, free from any ideological dogma” [1]. The Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022 – 2026 defines the goal: “Further development of the study and promotion of the history of Uzbekistan. Implementation of the Concept for the development of history as a science until 2030” [2].

3 Results and discussions

In the conditions of a new stage of development of society, the tasks of the social sciences are the deep and comprehensive assimilation of the rich historical experience of the peoples of Uzbekistan, saturated with complex, dramatic events, based on the principles of science, objectivity, historicism, and creative analysis of the historical process of multi-faceted events[3]. An important scientific source is the philosophical views of Turkestan educators in the process of increasing the moral, spiritual, environmental and political culture of student youth, which is especially important in the conditions of building a democratic, legal, secular, social state and civil society. Social sciences fulfill an important mission in instilling in students a sense of responsibility to society, civic duty, and high patriotism. "The significance of the study increases due to the positive content of the activities of the Jadids, which could serve as a good example for modern times. The Jadid movement played an important role in the formation and development of a modernized system of education, printing, national theater and drama, periodicals and other areas of intellectual life in the region. The most important concepts in their vocabulary were the words "tarakki" (progress), "Vatan" (Motherland), "millat" (nation), "maktab" (school), "Maorif" (enlightenment), "ilm" (science), "matbuot" (press), "theater", "kitobxona" (library), etc. Therefore, the experience of the Jadids is relevant in many areas of life and existence" [4].

The main goal of teaching social sciences in higher educational institutions at the present stage of the country's development is, first of all, to help students master the content of the modern history of Uzbekistan, philosophy, religious studies and other disciplines based on modern methods of analyzing the historical past, especially during the period of colonialism. To achieve the goal, the social sciences are given specific tasks. In the process of teaching social sciences, an important scientific source is the philosophical heritage of Turkestan enlighteners [5].

When it comes to conducting lectures and seminars in social disciplines, it is necessary to structure the educational material in a logic that will provide the most productive understanding of the basic patterns and directions of development of society in the conditions of the colonial policy of Russia and the Soviet period in the context of world history. This work requires the teacher to provide students with methodological recommendations for preparing for lectures and seminars, and other forms of independent work on the scientific works of Turkestan educators. It should be noted that "having emerged at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, Jadidism remained a relevant phenomenon until the end of the 1920s and to this day continues to attract significant attention from researchers not only in Central Asia, but also beyond, emphasizing its significance and influence on historical and cultural processes in the region" [6].

In the process of monitoring students' knowledge of activities, the content of the philosophical views of Turkestan educators, teachers should provide the necessary methodological assistance in their students' assimilation of materials. In the process of studying the scientific heritage of the Jadids, an important role is played by the organization of independent work of students based on new pedagogical technologies.

Taking into account the requirements of the credit-modular training system, training of competitive personnel, it is necessary to promptly provide students with a list of basic and additional literature revealing the scientific significance of the philosophical heritage of Turkestan enlighteners. A valuable scientific source in the study of the ideas of the Jadids are materials obtained from information network resources necessary for the study of social disciplines. This task requires a systematic improvement of the syllabus on the subject, supplementing it with new scientific publications, monographs, textbooks, textbooks in the social sciences, which reveal the reasons for the emergence, socio-political conditions, dissemination, goals, ideas of Turkestan educators in Central Asia[7].

In the preparation of competitive bachelors and masters for the new Uzbekistan, the research and publication of foreign scientists, where the educational activities of the Turkestan Jadids are deeply studied, are of theoretical and methodological importance[8].

It should be noted that the basis of social disciplines is the pluralistic nature of assessments of the most significant historical events during the period of the emergence and dissemination of the educational ideas of the Jadids, which contributes to the development of ideological and political pluralism in students, as well as the ability to conduct polemics and discussions on socio-political problems of social sciences in seminars. Thus, the content of social sciences suggests focusing on key moments in the history of Uzbekistan, when the formation and development of the philosophical views of the Jadids took place, revealing the presence of global trends, national-state and ethnocultural specifics in it [9].

The study of social disciplines is provided in the block of humanities and social sciences, which contributes to the preparation of highly qualified personnel of a new type - with a broad outlook and erudition, creative thinking, highly moral, with a mature civic position. In the process of studying, social sciences contribute to social foresight and forecasting, capable of solving the problems facing society at this stage of its reform and renewal, promoting the progress and prosperity of the Motherland.

Social Sciences contains materials on the activities of Turkestan historical educators, which are designed to promote the development of basic skills and competencies of bachelor's and master's degrees, especially future teachers, philosophers, and historians. They provide an opportunity to master the technologies of acquiring, using, and updating humanitarian knowledge, as well as the leading principles of working with a variety of sources. The acquired skills and competencies can be used in further professional activities.

State standards of higher education are based on a competency-based approach to the results of mastering social disciplines. As a result of mastering social disciplines, students should develop several competencies (knowledge, skills, and abilities).

As a result of mastering social disciplines and in-depth study of the activities of Turkestan Jadids, modern bachelors and masters will learn:

Firstly: the patterns and prerequisites for the emergence of the ideas of Turkestan enlighteners, the transformation of Jadidism into a socio-political movement on the territory of the Bukhara, Khiva and Kokand Khanates. The main stages of development and conditions for the dissemination of the basic democratic views of Turkestan enlighteners in the conditions of colonialism and the Soviet period. A movement of educators whose main goal was to fight against social and economic backwardness, stagnation, illiteracy and other shortcomings of society in the Turkestan region.

Secondly: the historical process occurring during the period of dissemination of the philosophical ideas of the Jadids at the end of the twentieth and early twentieth centuries. Content, purpose, essence of the main ideas of Turkestan enlighteners about the need to form the spiritual, moral and political culture of the individual, achieve independence in our country, their contribution to the formation of the foundation of the Third Renaissance. Important information for students is the activities of the Jadids to expose the essence of the colonial policy of the tsarist regime, which led to the socio-economic stagnation of the Turkestan region, and the shortcomings of the old educational system.

Thirdly: modern future cadres have knowledge about the activities of the leaders of Turkestan educators, their courage and heroism in disseminating new ideas in the field of education, culture, art, and the liberation of the homeland from the colonialists. In the study of the content of the philosophical ideas of the Jadids, the publication of newspapers and the publication of books, including their own works, play an important role.

Fourthly: the philosophical heritage of Turkestan enlighteners is an important factor in the formation of a high spiritual culture of thinking, which contributes to a generalized analysis and perception of historical reality. Having studied the scientific heritage, works, and works of Turkestan enlighteners, a modern student can explain the role and place of Uzbekistan in the development of world civilization;

Fifthly: independent analysis of the content of the educational ideas of the Jadids allows the student to possess scientific information in the interrelation of historical processes and the new stage of development of society, to identify problems of a social nature in the analysis of specific historical situations, possible socio-economic consequences at the present stage;

Sixth: to form, based on the study of the philosophical views of Turkestan enlighteners, scientifically substantiated theoretical conclusions, analysis using the methodology of historical research. He is proficient in methods and techniques for analyzing historical processes in the history of Uzbekistan, which had a priority influence on the formation of the philosophical heritage of Turkestan enlighteners. Also, an in-depth study of the creativity of Turkestan enlighteners helps the student in organizing independent work on primary sources about the activities of the Jadids and their contribution to the development of the spiritual culture of the people of our country.

Thus, an important element of the teacher's task in studying the heritage of Turkestan enlighteners is to use the possibilities of new pedagogical technologies and creatively connect it with the main material of the topic. It is necessary to improve methodological recommendations and assignments for independent work, topics for essays, scientific reports, essays, information about the educational teaching technologies used.

Current testing of the quality of mastery of the academic discipline during seminars and express tests. The plans of the seminars, methodological instructions for them, practical assignments, as well as a list of basic and additional literature on each topic are designed to help students organize conditions for self-preparation, master the skills of extracting, comprehending, and mastering scientific information, awaken attention to the underlying causes of the historical process, the desire to discover their roots and logic.

In conclusion, it is necessary to emphasize that the complex of recommended teaching methods in lectures and practical classes is based on innovative pedagogical technology of problem-based learning. The research atmosphere involves students in an active cognitive process through the analysis of specially selected primary sources concerning the activities of educators in Turkestan. The key conditions for the effectiveness of seminars should be reliance on creating a situation of dialogue. At the beginning of the lesson, it is important to diagnose students' readiness for dialogue. To do this, it is necessary to test the basic knowledge of the philosophical heritage

of Turkestan enlighteners, which they mastered at the previous lecture on the topic under study using a written express survey. Then, together with the students, you should find those exciting problems through which the meaning of the material being studied is revealed to them. Raising questions for discussion should take place in a system of problematic and controversial tasks.

4 Conclusion

It should be noted that the methodology for preparing for seminar classes should be based on the actual and potential level of development of students' knowledge, so the choice of methods can always vary. To optimize problem-based learning, variability is necessary, i.e., choosing a variant of the problem-based approach to studying educational material that best suits the level of a given academic group. The block of questions for each topic does not pretend to develop professional historian skills in students, but focuses on developing the ability to update primary knowledge about the most important events in the history of their native land, establish, systematize historical facts, as well as compare, generalize, contrast events, give them own assessment and draw appropriate conclusions.

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